

The Kinetics of Coagulation of Titanium Dioxide Sol.

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Smoluchowski (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1917, **92**, 129) proposed the following equation to represent the kinetics of rapid coagulation of a sol by electrolytes,

$$\Sigma_n = \frac{n_o}{1 + kn_o t} = \frac{n_o}{1 + \frac{t}{T}}$$

where n_o = the number of particles before the coagulation begins, K = velocity constant, t = the time since mixing of the electrolyte with the sol, T = specific coagulation time, given by the expression

$$T = \frac{1}{kn_o} = \frac{1}{4\pi D r n_o}$$

r being the radius of the sphere of attraction and D the diffusion constant.

If Σ_n , which represents the same stage of coalescence, has a fixed value then

$$\frac{t}{T} = \frac{t_1}{T_1} = \frac{t_2}{T_2} \dots\dots\dots$$

or $t : t_1 : t_2 \dots\dots\dots = T : T_1 : T_2 \dots\dots\dots$

where t, t_1, t_2 , etc., are the times since mixing of the electrolytes of various concentration and T, T_1, T_2 , etc., are the corresponding values of T for various mixtures. Since the values of $T, T_1, T_2, \dots\dots$ are fixed, their ratio is also fixed and should be independent of the stage of coalescence.

This theory has been verified by Zsigmondy (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1918, **92**, 600), Westgren and Reitstötter (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1918, **92**, 750) and by van Arkel (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1920, **39**, 656).

For slow coagulation Smoluchowski has proposed the following expression :

$$T = \frac{1}{k_1 n_o} = \frac{1}{8\pi D r n_o}$$

He distinguishes rapid coagulation from the slow one in the sense that in the former all the collisions are fruitful in bringing about the coalescence of the micelles while in the latter only a small

fraction of this is effective. This expression for slow coagulation has been confirmed by Westgren (*Ark. Matem. Astron. Fys.*, 1918, **13**, No. 14) and by Mukherjee and Majumdar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 794) up to a certain stage of coalescence.

It has been pointed out, however, by Miyazawa (*J. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1912, **33**, 1179), Ishizaka (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1913, **83**, 97), Gann (*Koll-Chem. Beih.*, 1916, **8**, 65), Lottermoser (*Kolloid Z.*, 1914, **15**, 145) and others that Smoluchowski's expression is not valid in the sensitive range of the electrolyte concentration. According to them, the coagulation is autocatalytic in nature and the coagulation velocity is best represented by the equation :

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k(1 + bx)(1 - x).$$

Desai (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1928, **24**, 181) has studied the kinetics of coagulation of thorium hydroxide sol and has examined the validity of the Smoluchowski's equation and of the equation given above. Patel and Desai (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, **26**, 128) have studied the coagulation of thorium hydroxide sol during the progress of dialysis of the sol and have found that the purity and the concentration of the colloid are necessary factors in determining the autocatalytic nature of the coagulation process.

The coagulation of titanium dioxide sol by electrolytes during the progress of dialysis has been studied in the present investigation and an attempt has been made to examine the validity of Smoluchowski's equation. The method used by Mukherjee and Majumdar (*loc. cit.*) has been employed to measure the rate of coagulation. The titanium dioxide sol is not a coloured one, nor any change in colour takes place during coagulation and hence the objections raised by Desai (*loc. cit.*) against this method do not apply to this case.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the sol.—Titanium dioxide sol was first prepared by Graham (*Phil. Trans.*, 1861, **151**, 213), by adding hydrochloric acid solution to sodium titanate. Mazumdar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 357) prepared the sol by adding titanium tetrachloride to distilled water, keeping the mixture at 18° and then dialysing it at room temperature. The sol prepared by both these methods was very unstable and coagulated before the chloride ions were removed.

In the present investigation the sol was prepared as follows: The titanium hydroxide was precipitated by adding ammonium hydroxide to titanium tetrachloride and was washed with hot water till free from ammonia. The suspension of the precipitate in a large volume of water was boiled and at certain intervals, 2*N* hydrochloric acid solution was added in small amounts until a clear sol was obtained. The total volume of the sol was kept constant by replacing the evaporated water from time to time. The sol thus prepared was transferred to a parchment bag which had been allowed to remain dipping in distilled water for 48 hours, and dialysed. During the dialysis no titanium was detected in the dialysate. The colloid content of the sol was found to be 1.2 g. of colloidal TiO₂ per litre.

Method of following the coagulation velocity.—A parallel beam of light from a 25 c. p. lamp, enclosed in an asbestos box having a rectangular window, was made to fall on a rectangular optical glass cell filled with distilled water, whereby the heat rays were absorbed. It next fell on an optical glass cell containing the colloidal solution and finally on a thermopile which was connected to a sensitive galvanometer. The current feeding the lamp was maintained at a constant value. The deflection of the galvanometer with distilled water alone in the colloidal cell was 200 mm. and it remained constant throughout.

In a test tube 5 c.c. of the colloid were taken and in another a solution of the electrolyte, just sufficient to produce coagulation in about 30—35 minutes: the volume of the latter was made up to 5 c.c. by the addition of distilled water.

The mixture (electrolyte + water) was added to the colloid by gently pouring it down the sides of the test tube and the time of mixing the electrolyte with the colloid was noted. The same method of mixing the electrolyte with the colloid was used throughout. The mixture was then transferred to the colloid cell, the thermopile exposed to light at definite intervals and the deflections of the galvanometer were noted.

The relative distances between the various parts of the apparatus were kept constant throughout the series of experiments.

The titanium dioxide sol dialysed for 4, 10, 18, 24 and 32 days was studied using different concentrations of sodium chloride and magnesium chloride. The effect of dilution on the coagulation velocity was also investigated and for this purpose the sol is designated as A, A/2 and A/4.

The results obtained with sodium chloride and the sol dialysed for 4 days and those with magnesium chloride and the sol dialysed for 10 days are shown graphically in Figures 1 to 3. The deflection differences were obtained by subtracting the observed deflection from that given by 5 c. c. of the sol + 5 c. c. of water.

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

TABLE I
 TiO₂ Sol dialysed for 4 days.
 Electrolyte NaCl, 1N.

Deflection diff. in mm.	Amount of the electrolyte in c.c.				<i>t</i>	<i>t</i> ₁	<i>t</i> ₂	<i>t</i> ₃	<i>t</i> ₄	<i>T</i>	Ratios.			
	4	3	2.75	2.5							2	<i>T</i> ₁ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₂ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₃ / <i>T</i>
5	1	3	7	10	18	1	8	7	10	18				
7	1	4	9	12	20	1	4	9	12	20				
10	2	6	12	14	25	1	3	6	7	12.5				
13	2	8	14	17	30	1	4	7	8.5	15				
15	2	8	15	20	32	1	4	7.5	10	16				
18	3	9	16	30	36	1	3	5.3	10	12				
21	3	9	12	...	40	1	3	4	...	13.3				
24	4	9	19	...	46	1	2.25	4.75	...	11.5				

TABLE II.

TiO₂ Sol dialysed for 10 days.

Electrolyte NaCl, 0.25N.

Deflection diff. in mm.	Amount of the electrolyte in c.c.			Ratios.				
	<i>t</i>	<i>t</i> ₁	<i>t</i> ₂	<i>t</i> ₃	<i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₁ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₂ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₃ / <i>T</i>
	3	2.75	2.5	2				
5	1	2	3	9	1	2	3	9
8	2	4	5	18	1	2	2.5	9
11	2	4	8	25	1	2	4	12.25
14	3	6	10	35	1	2	3.3	11.7
17	3	9	14	45	1	3	4.7	15
20	5	11	18	60	1	2.2	3.6	12
23	6	14	23	73	1	2.33	3.83	12
26	7	17	28	...	1	2.43	4	...
29	9	20	33	...	1	2.2	3.7	...
32	10	23	39	...	1	2.3	3.9	...

TABLE III_s

TiO₂ Sol dialysed for 25 days

Electrolyte NaCl, 0.005N.

Deflection dif. in mm.	Amount of the electrolyte in c. c.			Ratios.			
	<i>t</i>	<i>t</i> ₁	<i>t</i> ₂	<i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₁ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₂ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₃ / <i>T</i>
2	0.1	0.2	0.4	1	2	4	7
4	0.2	0.4	0.9	1	2	4.5	6.5
6	0.3	0.6	1.2	1	2	4	6.66
8	0.4	0.8	1.7	1	2	4.25	7.5
10	0.5	1.0	2.3	1	2	4.6	...
12	0.6	1.2	2.8	1	2	4.7	...
14	0.7	1.5	3.5	1	2.15	5	...
16	0.8	1.7	4.5	1	2.12	5.6	...
18	0.9	2.0	5.7	1	2.2	6.3	...
20	1	2.6	8	1	2.6	8	...

TABLE IV
TiO₂ Sol dialysed for 10 days.
 Electrolyte MgCl₂, 0.5N.

Deflection diff. in mm.	Amount of the electrolyte in c.c.				T	Ratios.		
	t	t ₁	t ₂	t ₃		T ₁ /T	T ₂ /T	T ₃ /T
	3	2.75	2.5	2				
5	0.8	2	6	10	1	2.5	7.5	12.5
8	1	3	9	14	1	3	9	14
11	1.7	4.5	11	17.5	1	2.6	6.5	10.3
14	3	6	13	20.5	1	2	4.3	6.8
17	4	7.5	14.5	24	1	1.9	3.73	6
20	5	9	16.5	27	1	1.8	3.2	5.4
23	6	10	18.5	31	1	1.66	3.08	5.2
26	7.5	11.5	20.5	35	1	1.5	2.7	4.7
29	9	13	23	40	1	1.44	2.6	4.4
32	10	14	25	50	1	1.45	2.5	

TABLE V.
 TiO₂ Sol dialysed for 18 days.

Deflection diff. in mm.	Amount of the electrolyte in c.c.			Ratios.				
	<i>t</i>	<i>t</i> ₁	<i>t</i> ₂	<i>t</i> ₃	<i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₁ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₂ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₃ / <i>T</i>
	3	2.75	2.5	2				
2	0.6	1	2.5	5.5	1	2	5	11
5	1	2	6	12	1	2	3	12
8	1.7	3.25	9.5	19.5	1	1.9	5.6	11.5
11	2.5	4.75	13	29	1	1.9	5.2	11.6
14	3	6	16.5	—	1	2	5.5	—
17	3.75	8	20	—	1	2.5	5.3	—
20	4.75	10	24	—	1	2.1	5	—

TABLE VI.

*TiO₂ Sol dialysed for 25 days.*Electrolyte MgCl₂, 0.008 N.

Deflection diff. in mm.	Amount of the electrolyte in c.c.				Ratios.					
	<i>t</i>	<i>t</i> ₁	<i>t</i> ₂	<i>t</i> ₃	<i>t</i> ₄	<i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₁ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₂ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₃ / <i>T</i>	<i>T</i> ₄ / <i>T</i>
2	0.1	0.2	0.35	0.65	1.5	1	2	3.5	6	15
4	0.2	0.3	0.7	1.3	3.5	1	1.5	3.5	6.5	17.5
6	0.3	0.4	1.1	2.1	6	1	1.3	3.66	6.6	20
8	0.4	0.55	1.6	3.2	10	1	1.25	4	8	25
10	0.5	0.75	2	3	...	1	1.5	5	10	...
12	0.6	0.9	2.55	6.2	...	1	1.5	4.1	10.3	...
14	0.7	1.1	3.2	9	...	1	1.5	4.3	12.8	...
16	0.8	1.4	4	1	1.6	5
18	0.9	1.7	5	1	1.75	5.5
20	1	2	5.3	1	1.9	5.3

DISCUSSION.

The values of t , for the same stage of coalescence, when different amounts of the electrolytes are added to the same volume of the sol, have been obtained from the coagulation velocity curves for "A" sols and the ratios $\frac{T_1}{T}$, $\frac{T_2}{T}$ etc., have been calculated for various stages of coalescence. The ratios obtained in the case of sodium chloride and the sol dialysed for 4, 10 and 25 days and those in the case of magnesium chloride and the sol dialysed for 10, 18 and 25 days are given in Tables I to VI for illustration.

It is observed that these ratios become more and more constant as the amount of the electrolyte is increased and as the sol gets purer. The percentage deviations of the ratios from the mean values are considerable for small amounts of electrolytes. This appears to indicate that Smoluchowski's equation is true only under restricted conditions.

It will be seen from Figs. 1 to 3 that the coagulation velocity curves for "A" sol dialysed for 4 days are S-shaped and that the S-shaped tendency of the curves for the same amount of the electrolyte becomes less and less with an increase in the dilution of the sol. It is found that the S-shaped nature of the curves disappears as the sol is dialysed further: the curves for sols dialysed for more than 18 days do not give S-shaped curves when they are coagulated by any concentration of sodium chloride.

In the case of sols coagulated by magnesium chloride similar results have been obtained.

It appears that the S-shaped nature of the coagulation velocity curves is intimately connected with the peptising ions present in the sols. Similar observations have been made by Patel and Desai (*loc. cit.*).

These results can be explained, as done by Patel and Desai (*loc. cit.*) in the case of thorium hydroxide sol, on the first and second critical potential of Freundlich. But the recent investigations by Desai and his collaborators (*Current Science*, 1932, 1, 38) on the measurement of charge on the colloid particles during the progress of dialysis of a sol, indicate that the charge does not decrease continuously as the dialysis is carried out for longer time. They find in the case of the thorium hydroxide sol that the charge

increases at first and then begins to decrease. This would mean that for the first few days of dialysis, the tendency of the sol should be to give rise to increased S-shape to the coagulation velocity curves. It is, therefore, necessary to carry out the charge measurements of titanium dioxide sol during the progress of dialysis and to study the coagulation velocity during the period when an increase in the charge on the colloid particles is taking place.

However, the results arrived at in this investigation confirm Patel and Desai's view that the concentration of a colloid is an important factor in determining the autocatalytic nature of the coagulation velocity curves.

SUMMARY.

1. The coagulation of titanium dioxide sol by sodium chloride and magnesium chloride has been followed by the thermopile method during the progress of dialysis of the sol.

2. The applicability of Smoluchowski's equation to the coagulation of the sol has been tested and it is found that it applies only for a limited range of the concentration of the coagulator.

3. The coagulation velocity curves (deflection differences against time) are S-shaped for sols dialysed up to 18 days: sols dialysed for longer time do not show the autocatalytic nature of the coagulation process.

4. The results of this investigation confirm the observations of Patel and Desai (*loc. cit.*) that (i) the S-shaped nature of the coagulation velocity curves is intimately connected with the peptising ions present and (ii) the concentration of the colloid is an important factor in determining the autocatalytic nature of the coagulation velocity curves.

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